

The 2024 EU Parliamentary Elections in Romania

An election dominated by local issues

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The political context: the end of an electoral cycle and a joint election

Romania had a “super-electoral” year in 2024, including four types of elections – local, parliamentary, presidential, and European. The 2020-2024 cycle was a unique one, shaped by the COVID-19 pandemic, a rare event that significantly altered basic patterns of human interaction. The popular consensus was that the 2024 elections would be more punishing than usual for the parties in power and would reward those that made the pandemic a central issue in their campaign. The same electoral cycle also included the Russia-Ukraine conflict (2022-present), which muddied matters further, as Romania has both a common border with Ukraine to the North and the East, and a complex relationship with the Republic of Moldova, a former Soviet republic.

The political scene at the beginning of 2024 was dominated by five parliamentary parties: the Social Democratic Party (PSD, centre-left), the National Liberal Party (PNL, centre-right), the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians (UDMR, centre-right and representing the interests of the Hungarian minority), the Save Romania Union (USR), and the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR). The first three, PSD, PNL, and UDMR, have existed since 1989, while USR joined the Parliament in 2016 and AUR in 2020. USR is mostly known as an anti-corruption party that has promised a new approach to politics, while AUR is generally considered a right-wing nationalist and populist party (Soare and Collini, 2024). Several other minor parties are worth mentioning: the Popular Movement Party (PMP, a centre-right party), SOS România (which split from AUR, known mainly for its extremely vocal populist and nationalist leader, Diana Şoşocă), REPER (a centrist party that broke away from USR).

The previous elections (2020, local and parliamentary) took place in the middle of the pandemic, leading to the lowest turnout rates ever recorded in

Romania: 46% for the local elections and 32% for the parliamentary elections. The big surprise was that the newly formed AUR, the only party to make the government's response to the COVID-19 crisis a central theme of its campaign, became the fourth-largest parliamentary party, securing more than 9% of the votes. The remaining votes were distributed among PSD (29%), PNL (25%), USR (15%), and UDMR (6%). The Liberals managed to assemble a short-lived governing coalition (PNL-USR-UDMR) which broke down in September 2021, mostly due to frictions between PNL and USR. After two months of negotiations, PSD and PNL formed a new governing coalition, with UDMR as a minor partner. The coalition was designed to operate under a rotation system, with the Prime Minister position alternating every 18 months between PSD and PNL.

Consequently, at the beginning of 2024, Romania was relatively stable politically, with PSD and PNL having governed together for over two years. The main political issue on the agenda was the rise of AUR, although this was more of a concern for political parties than for the general population. In economic terms, although 2022 and 2023 were characterised by high inflation rates (exceeding 10% from March 2022 to June 2023), unemployment has stayed at 5%-6% over the last four years. The most important issues for the population were rising prices and a general sense of fear concerning the future of the Russia-Ukraine conflict

The 2024 election calendar became one of the key negotiation points within the governing coalition. By February 2024, two decisions were made. First, PSD and PNL decided to form a joint list for the European Parliament (EP) elections, to minimise the votes that could be obtained by the Eurosceptic AUR (Beşliu, 2024). While PSD and PNL had run on joint lists before in local and national elections, this decision was a novelty for the EP elections, because it brought together the local representatives of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D) and the European People's Party (EPP).

Second, citing concerns about potential voter fatigue, financial considerations, and low turnout, the governing coalition decided to hold the local and EP elections at the same time. This was mainly intended to maximise turnout, given that low turnout favours small, extremist parties (such as AUR) while high turnout benefits the larger political parties. When it comes to Romania, local elections are seen as a way to increase turnout, as candidates have a strong incentive to mobilise voters. Of particular importance are the mayors, who can be more effective in encouraging people to vote. After the 2020 local elections, PSD (30.3%) and PNL (34.6%) controlled almost two-thirds of municipalities.

The Electoral system: EP election impacted by the lack of a unified electoral method

For both local and European elections, the minimum voting age is 18 and voting is not compulsory. In the case of the EU Parliamentary elections, Romania is treated as a single national constituency, in which all 33 members of the European Parliament are elected under a closed list proportional representation system (PR). In the case of local elections, citizens have the right to vote for the mayor of the locality in which they are legally residing (using a first-past-the-post system [FPTP]), for local and county councilors (using a closed list PR system). As a result, voters received four ballots, one for the EP elections and three for the local elections, which complicated both the voting process and the vote-counting process, confusing voters and officials (VotCorect.ro, 2024:7).

Romania has about 4 million emigrants, equivalent to 17% of its population (McAuliffe and Triandafyllidou, 2021), who are working and living abroad, primarily in Europe. According to Romanian legislation, citizens living abroad can vote for the EP elections at any location of their choice, but for local elections, they can only vote within Romania, in the locality where they have their legal residence. This meant that a low turnout was expected from the diaspora in the EP elections.

With regard to the candidates, the closed lists are the subject of intense intra-party negotiations. Romania has very strict requirements for running in the EP elections: political parties must gather 200,000 signatures, while independent candidates need 100,000 signatures in support of their candidacy. This requirement creates an incentive for potential candidates to obtain signatures in any possible way, legal or not. The lists of signatures are only counted but they are not thoroughly verified, as there is no standardised procedure for doing so (VotCorect.ro, 2024, 14). To win seats, political parties are required to pass the threshold (5% of valid votes) while independent candidates must exceed the national electoral coefficient (the total number of valid votes divided by the number of seats, 33). In total, 12 political parties/alliances and four independent candidates contested the 33 seats reserved for Romania in the European Parliament. Two of the independent candidates were elected in 2019 as members of the EP on USR's list but have since left the party. The other two independents were relatively unknown politicians. Similarly, about half of the parties likely ran purely for visibility, as they had no real chance of reaching the threshold.

The campaign and results: big parties - local issues, small parties - European issues

According to opinion polls published between January and May 2024, despite the large number of candidates, only a limited few had a genuine chance of winning seats. Although opinion polls are unreliable in Romania, they still influence public opinion, so the predictions for the EP elections are presented here. The PSD-PNL Alliance was estimated to receive about 40%-50% of the vote, AUR between 14% and 28%, and UDMR no more than 6%. USR (which is part of Renew Europe) joined forces with the Force of the Right (FD, which split from PNL in 2021) and the People's Movement Party (PMP), both of which are affiliated with the EPP. Their alliance, the United Right Alliance (ADU) was projected to secure between 12% and 21% of the vote. Finally, SOS România, a party led by a prominent former senator of AUR, was expected to obtain no more than 6% of the vote.

The huge variations in the opinion poll estimates could indicate either a highly volatile political environment or unreliable polling. The consensus among sociologists and political scientists in Romania is that these estimates are proof that opinion polls are being manipulated by political parties, some of which have very close ties to the polling companies (Pora, 2024). Regular voters were therefore forced to decide which party to vote for without having the correct information about the likelihood of success for the rival parties.

Combining the local and EP elections made political parties focus almost exclusively on the local elections, and to tailor their electoral campaigns accordingly. The PSD-PNL Alliance was virtually absent from the EP campaign, as both parties decided to focus mainly on the local elections, where they ran on separate lists (except in a few cities where they ran on joint lists in an effort to block USR from winning the municipality).

As a result, the main political parties abandoned the EP election campaign, leaving behind three types of political actors. First, the Eurosceptic parties (AUR and SOS România), which seemed to be the most active, campaigned on a platform to protect the national interests of 'true Romanians'. Second, smaller parties and alliances sought to reelect their incumbent members of the European Parliament (MEPs) by running campaigns centred on their accomplishments in office. Finally, independent candidates (in particular Nicu Ștefănuță and Vlad Gheorghe, both MEPs elected on USR's list in 2019) also ran campaigns focused on European issues.

It should be noted that Romanian legislation allows political parties to direct significant funds towards mass media outlets, leading to “biased coverage primarily in favor of the governing coalition [... by a] pliant media that fails to hold government to account” (Media Freedom Rapid Response, 2024). As a result, smaller political parties and independent candidates mostly campaigned online and in person, which put them at a disadvantage compared to the main political parties, which had access to channels with a larger audience.

The EP election took place in Romania on June 9, 2024. According to official data, 18.03 million people were expected to vote in the 2024 EP elections. About 9.4 million people voted, corresponding to a turnout rate of 52.4% (the official results are available at <https://prezenta.roaep.ro/europarlamentare09062024/romania/counties> and <https://europarlamentare2024.bec.ro/rezultate/>). These numbers include votes from abroad. As is usually the case in Romania, youth turnout was slightly lower. Voters aged 18-24 represented just 8% of the total vote, compared to 9% of the population, while voters aged 25-34 made up 12% of the total vote, compared to 14% of the population. In total, only 20% of the vote came from those under 35, a group that represents 23% of the Romanian population (author’s calculation based on official data available at <https://prezenta.roaep.ro/europarlamentare09062024/romania/counties> and <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table, table POP105A>).

The results of the EP election are presented in Table 1. In contrast to the 2019 elections, more parties opted to form alliances for the 2024 elections. The most significant outcome in 2024 was that the Euro-sceptic parties, AUR and SOS România, managed to secure almost 20% of the vote, which brought them 8 seats in the EP. The two parties in the governing coalition ran on a single list and managed to maintain their 2019 performance (48.6% in 2024, compared to 49.5% in 2019). The biggest loser in 2024 was USR, which dropped from 22.36% in 2019 to just 8.7% in 2024, despite being in an alliance with PMP. In summary, the incumbents, PSD and PNL, maintained their dominance but switched positions, while the opposition underwent significant changes compared to 2019, with the Euro-sceptic parties gaining significant ground.

Table 1. EP election results, Romania, 2024

Political party*	Political group in the European Parliament	Results			
		Vote share (%)	Change compared to 2019	Seats	Change compared to 2019
PSD - Partidul Social Democrat (member of the PSD-PNL Alliance)	S&D - The Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats group in the European Parliament	48.6	22.5% in 2019	11	+3
PNL - Partidul Național Liberal (member of the PSD-PNL Alliance)	EPP - The European People's Party group (Christian Democrats)		27.0% in 2019	8	-2
AUR - <i>Alianța pentru Unirea Românilor</i>	ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group	14.9	+14.9	6	+6
USR - <i>Uniunea Salvați România</i> (member of ADU - <i>Alianța Dreapta Unită</i>)	Renew Europe Group	8.7	22.36% in 2019	2	-6
PMP - <i>Partidul Mișcarea Populară</i> (member of ADU - <i>Alianța Dreapta Unită</i>)	Renew Europe Group		5.76% in 2019	1	-1
FD - <i>Forța Dreptei</i> (member of ADU - <i>Alianța Dreapta Unită</i>)	n/a		0	0	-
UDMR	EPP - The European People's Party group (Christian Democrats)	6.5	1.24	2	=
<i>SOS România</i>	NI - Non-attached Members	5	new	2	+2
Nicu Ștefănuță (opposition)	Greens/EFA - The Greens/European Free Alliance group	3.1	new	1	+1
Other parties	---	13.2	-3.92	0	-2

Source: <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/national-results/romania/2024-2029/> - *Parties in government are in bold.

The consequences: the rise of Eurosceptic parties

The results of the 2024 EP election in Romania can be summarised in four key points. First, turnout was in line with the European Union average, boosted by the decision to combine the EP and the local elections, but tempered by low diaspora participation: only 216,002 people voted abroad, compared to

944,077 in the second round of the 2019 presidential elections (data available at <https://prezenta.roaep.ro/europarlamentare09062024/abroad/precincts> and <https://prezenta.bec.ro/prezidentiale24112019/abroad-precincts>).

Second, there is strong evidence to suggest that the decision to combine the EP and local elections was aimed at benefiting the governing parties, rather than keeping extremist parties away from the EP: AUR and SOS România received 20% of the vote and obtained 8 seats in the EP, the same number as PNL. One would have expected the results for PSD and PNL to be worse had it not been for the additional mobilisation carried out by their mayors. At the same time, it would be difficult for PSD and PNL to argue they have kept the extremists at bay, given that the ECR gained six MEPs from Romania in 2024, to which one should also add the two MEPs from SOS România, who have been considered too radical even for the ECR, PFE, or ESN.

Third, the results also show how fragmentation and political party infighting affect both electoral outcomes and voter representation. The clearest example is USR, which held eight seats in the 2019-2024 term. This time, the MEPs elected on USR's list in 2019 ran for USR, REPER, and two ran as independent candidates. In doing so, they wasted 556,333 votes, equivalent to 6% of the valid votes.

Finally, this round of elections represented yet another missed opportunity for Romanian citizens to engage in a discussion on European issues and cast informed votes. The responsibility for this rests primarily with the largest political parties, PSD and PNL, which chose, largely in their own interest, to ignore the EP elections and instead focus solely on the local elections, as well as planning for the upcoming parliamentary and presidential elections.

Only a day before sending this paper to the publisher, Romania held general elections (December 1st, 2024). The results reveal that Euro-sceptic parties have gained even more ground since the EP elections, securing about 37% of the vote for the Parliament (21% for AUR, 8% for SOS România, and 7% for POT - the Party of the Young People - a party founded in March 2023 that did not stand in the European elections). However, mainstream parties (PSD, PNL, USR, and UDMR) collectively received 67% of the vote and are expected to either form a grand coalition (which seems unlikely) or a majority coalition composed of PSD, PNL, and UDMR, similar to the current government (which only comprises PSD and PNL).

References

Beșliu, Raluca (2024), “Romania’s joint electoral list: Strategic move or threat to democracy”, *The Parliament*. Available at: <https://www.theparliamentmagazine.eu/news/article/romanias-joint-electoral-list-strategic-move-or-threat-to-democracy> (accessed July 29 2024).

Coaliția Vot Corect (2024), Raport final privind observarea alegerilor locale și parlamentare, 9 iunie 2024. București: Coaliția Vot Corect. Available online https://expertforum.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/VC_Raport-final-observare_alegeri_9iunie.pdf. Last accessed: July 30, 2024.

Mcauliffe, Marie and Triandafyllidou, Anna (eds.) (2021), *World Migration Report 2022*. Geneva: International Organization for Migration (IOM).

Media Freedom Rapid Response (2024), “Media Freedom Mission to Romania questions fairness of electoral coverage”. Available at: <https://ipi.media/media-freedom-mission-to-romania-questions-fairness-of-electoral-coverage/> (accessed July 30 2024).

Pora, Andreea (2024), “Sondaje sau pariuri ?”, *Europa Liberă România*. Available at: <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/sondaje-sau-pariuri-de-ce-sunt-atat-de-diferite-sondajele-de-opinie-pentru-alegerile-prezidentiale-si-cine-castiga-din-asta/33172180.html> (accessed October 30 2024).

Soare, Sorina and Collini, Mattia (2024), “Romanian Parties and Post-Communist Democracy”, In: Lavinia Stan et Diance Vancea (Eds.), *Post-Communist Progress and Stagnation at 35: The Case of Romania*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, p. 133-157.